

removed and their reproductive rate was assessed indirectly by counting the emerging nymphs from plants that received different insecticides. The counted nymphs were removed every day, and counting went on until all eggs hatched.

The number of nymphs hatching was the criterion for evaluation of the resurgence potential of the insecticides. The number of nymphs differed significantly among treatments (see figure). The highest number emerged from plants sprayed 3 times with decamethrin. The last insecticide sprayed generally had a decisive role in inducing

or preventing BPH resurgence. In treatments where plants were sprayed twice with Perthane and then by decamethrin or methyl parathion the level of BPH resurgence was equal to that where plants were sprayed three times with methyl parathion. When Perthane was sprayed last, the number of BPH nymphs did not increase, regardless of the insecticides used in previous sprayings. This implied that even if resurgence-causing insecticide had inadvertently been used, the population buildup could be controlled by use of an insecticide that would negate the resurgence effect. ■

T. W. Mew, IRRI pathologist, on a September 1979 visit to the institute, suggested that the disease might be caused by *Erwinia* sp. S. Devadath from the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, examined the crop on 31 October and suggested that the disease might be bacterial foot rot caused by *Erwinia chrysanthemi*, which was reported by Goto in Japan in 1979. This may be the first report of the disease in India. The disease is being further investigated. ■

A new record of rice transitory yellowing virus in northern Thailand

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Yellowing symptoms of rice plants similar to those of rice transitory yellowing disease (RTYV) occurred on wet-season rice at the late growth stage in August–September 1979 in Chiengrai and Chiengmai, northern Thailand. At locations where disease symptoms were observed, 18 to 32% of the hills were infested.

Electromicroscopic observations of dip preparations and ultrathin sections of diseased plants revealed that bullet-shaped virus particles (90 x 120 nm in dip preparations, 90 x 180 nm in ultrathin sections) were similar to those found in diseased leaves infected with RTYV in Taiwan and Okinawa, Japan. In ultrathin sections, the virus particles were observed in phloem cells of diseased plants. *Nephotettix nigropictus* and *N. cincticeps* transmitted the virus effectively and in a persistent manner. The virus incubation period in the insects was about 2 weeks; the viruliferous insects often remained infective during their entire life span.

The virus belonging to the rhabdovirus group was identified as rice transitory

The influence of insecticide used in spray sequence on brown planthopper reproductive rate. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University and IRRI.

A new bacterial disease of rice

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Most plants in a 2-ha plot of the variety Pankaj were observed to be drying during a routine field visit to the Institute farm in 1979 kharif. The crop was in the maximum-tillering stage. The growth of the infected plants was somewhat stunted. From a distance the disease appeared to

be the kresak stage of bacterial blight. But a closer examination showed black and rotting basal internodes and enclosing leaf sheaths. The gummy, rotted portion emitted a foul odor. Core portions of tillers dried first; sometimes the central leaf dried much earlier than the other leaves and the symptoms resembled those of stem borer damage. The dried leaves were erect and straw color. Only a few tillers in most infected hills remained healthy. Roots were normal but dried tillers could easily be pulled out.

yellowing virus. This is the first report of the occurrence of this disease in the tropics. ■

Transmission of rice tungro virus from stubbles of different rice varieties 30, 60, 90, and 120 days after harvest. West Bengal, India, 1978.

Variety	Transmission (%) in seedlings			
	30 days	60 days	90 days	120 days
Ratna	10	0	0	0
Pankaj	10	5	0	0
Cauvery	0	0	0	0
IET1441	0	0	0	0
IR579	20	10	0	0
IET2295	0	0	0	0
IET2914	30	20	10	0
Jaya	20	10	0	0
IR8	10	0	0	0
Laghu	20	10	0	0
Kathamuk	20	10	0	0
Rajmalati	20	5	0	0
Kalamkathi	10	0	0	0
Lakhansail	20	10	0	0
Sachimohan	20	10	0	0
Jhulur	10	0	0	0
Dhushri	20	10	0	0
Dudshar	10	0	0	0
Ashanlaya	20	10	0	0
Madhumalati	20	10	0	0

Induced 7/20/80
Further studies on the potential of rice stubble for spreading tungro in West Bengal, India

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A previous study on the potential of rice stubble in spreading tungro in West Bengal confirmed that infected stubbles of TN1 plants can act as a virus source and maintain the virus for 75 days. The same procedure was used to test the infected stubbles of high yielding and local varieties for efficiency in transmitting virus.

Of the nine high yielding varieties (Ratna, Pankaj, Cauvery, IET1441, IR579, IET2295, IET2914, Jaya, and IR8) and 11 local varieties (Laghu, Kathamuk, Rajmalati, Kalamkathi, Lakhansail, Sachimohan, Jhulur, Dhushri, Dudshar, Ashanlaya, and Madhumalati) tested (see table), Ratna and IR8

retained the virus in the stubbles for only 30 days; Pankaj, IR579, and Jaya for 60 days; and IET2914 for 90 days. The stubbles of Cauvery, IET1441, and IET2295 carried no virus.

Of the local varieties tested, Kalamkathi and Dudshar carried the virus in the stubbles for only 30 days;

the stubbles of Laghu, Rajmalati, Lakhansail, Sachimohan, Ashanlaya, and Madhumalati retained the virus for 60 days; and those of Kathamuk and Dhushri for 90 days (see table). The research was funded by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi. ■

Effect of transplanting date and seedling age at transplanting on spread of tungro

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Experiments were conducted at the plant virus experimental field to determine the effect of transplanting date and of

seedling age at transplanting on the spread of tungro virus disease in a rice crop during 1978 kharif. The Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi, funded the research.

In the first experiment 25-day-old TN1 seedlings were transplanted at 5-day intervals in 3-m² replicated plots provided with uniform inoculum for tungro virus (1 infected plant/plot). The

number of plants with tungro symptoms was recorded at 3- to 6-day intervals until the end of September.

Transplanting date had pronounced effects on the spread of tungro (see table). The spread of the disease increased when the transplanting date gradually shifted from mid-July to the first week of August, when spread became maximum. With subsequent shifts of

Effect of transplanting date and age at transplanting of TN1 seedlings on the spread of rice tungro virus (RTV) disease during 1978 kharif (Jul–Nov) and the corresponding vector population in the field, West Bengal, India.

Date of observation	LH ^a (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)			
	A	N		A	N		A	N		A	N		A	N				
	Effect of transplanting date of 25-day-old TN1 seedlings																	
	16 Jul			21 Jul			26 Jul			1 Aug			6 Aug			11 Aug		
28 Jul	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—									
2 Aug	1	0	—	1	0	—	2	0	—	0	0	—						
7 Aug	0	2	—	4	2	—	3	9	—	3	10	—	3	5	—			
12 Aug	1	1	—	1	37	—	3	70	—	2	38	—	3	82	—	4	11	—
17 Aug	1	0	—	0	15	—	0	20	—	0	40	—	0	43	—	2	3	—

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